

1 **Supramolecular solvent-based microextraction of emerging**
2 **bisphenol A replacements (colour developers) in indoor dust**
3 **from public environments**

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20 **ABSTRACT**

21 Bisphenol A (BPA) is present in a wide variety of materials and it is a well-known
22 endocrine disruptor that is widespread in indoor and outdoor environments. For this
23 reason, industry has introduced a variety of replacements, such as Bisphenol S (BPS) or
24 Bisphenol F (BPF), and other less known structural analogs, such as BPS-MAE, D-8 or
25 TGSA. These emerging potential contaminants have been identified in thermal paper
26 products, according to recent studies, but their potential toxic effects and their migration
27 into the environment remain unclear. In this study, we report for the first time the
28 presence of emerging BPA replacements in indoor dust from public environments
29 (shops, restaurants, etc.). For this purpose, we optimized a novel supramolecular solvent
30 (SUPRAS)-based microextraction method. SUPRAS are multi-target solvents made up
31 of self-assembled amphiphiles. They offer multiple extraction interactions (dispersion,
32 polar, hydrophobic, etc.) and they constitute excellent candidates to develop generic and
33 fast sample treatment procedures at low cost. By this method, emerging BPA
34 replacements (BPS-MAE, D-8 and TGSA) were detected in dust at median
35 concentrations in the range $6 - 22 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (around ten times lower than BPS) with
36 detection frequencies in the range 50 – 90%. These results constitute a first insight into
37 the migration of emerging BPA replacements into the environment via indoor dust,
38 which is a common route of human exposure to contaminants.

39

40 **Keywords:** supramolecular solvents, indoor dust, bisphenol A, bisphenol S, BPS-MAE,
41 D-8, TGSA

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43 1. Introduction

44 Bisphenol A (BPA) or 4,4'-(propane-2,2-diyl)diphenol, is used worldwide and its
45 production volume is one of the highest in the industry. It is used in wide variety of
46 applications from food-related plastics (food-packaging, bottles, cookware, tableware,
47 etc.) to other materials, such as medical devices, printing inks, thermal paper, etc. BPA
48 can migrate into the environment because plastic contains non-polymerized monomer
49 residues or because it is released by ester bonds hydrolysis under heat or reaction with
50 the acid or basic contents of the bottles (Björnsdotter et al., 2017a). BPA has become an
51 ubiquitous environmental contaminant, which is present in river waters ($1.0 - 628 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
52 ¹) (Suzuki et al., 2004; Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2007; Ruiz et al., 2007; Yamazaki et
53 al., 2015), sediments ($3.94 - 2.2\cdot 10^6 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1} \text{ d.w.}$) (Terasaki et al., 2007; Liao et al.,
54 2012a; Wang et al., 2016), sewage sludge ($0.42 - 25,600 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) (Song et al., 2014; Lee
55 et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2015), air (indoor: $<0.1 - 1.8 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, outdoor: $<0.1 - 2.5 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
56 (Wilson et al., 2001) and dust ($535 - 9,730 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) (Geens et al., 2009). It has also been
57 widely detected in biological samples, such as blood ($0.79 - 7.12 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) (Owczarek
58 et al., 2018) saliva (mean of $3.64 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) (Lee et al., 2017) or urine (mean of $2.6 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)
59 (Casas et al., 2013). BPA is a well-known endocrine disruptor (Rochester, 2011), it is
60 capable to disrupt the thyroid hormone action, affecting vertebrate development (Zhang
61 et al., 2017) and it can act as neurodevelopmental toxicant too (Kinch et al., 2015).

62 In order to evade regulatory oversight and social pressure, industry has
63 introduced BPA replacements into the market. Replacements are usually structural
64 analogs to BPA with similar physicochemical properties and, subsequently, similar
65 potential toxicity (Gramec Skledar and Peterlin Masic, 2016; Russo et al., 2018).
66 Bisphenol S (BPS), bisphenol F (BPF), bisphenol B (BPB), bisphenol AF (BPAF),
67 bisphenol E (BPE), tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), bisphenol A diglycidyl ether

68 (BADGE) and bisphenol F diglycidyl ether (BFDGE) are common BPA replacements.
69 They are used in a variety of materials too, such as electronic equipment, cans' lacquer
70 coating, dental sealants and flame retarded products (Björnsdotter et al., 2017a). Due to
71 this massive utilization, they have also been widely reported in sediments (3.2 – 12.6
72 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), sewage sludge (12.8 – 4,730 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) or indoor dust (0.15 – 4.18 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), etc.
73 (sum of all detectable analogues including BPA) (Chen et al., 2016).

74 Other widespread use of BPA is thermal paper (Geens et al., 2012; Björnsdotter
75 et al., 2017a; Pivnenko, 2018). Replacements have also been introduced into the market
76 for this aim, namely BPS and other less known compounds such as 4-hydroxyphenyl 4-
77 isopropoxyphenyl Sulfone (D-8), 4,4'-sulfonylbis(2-allylphenol) (TGSA), 4-((4-
78 (allyloxy)phenyl)sulfonyl)phenol (BPS-MAE), Pergafast 201 and D-90 (US EPA,
79 2015). Although there are some recent studies about the presence of these compounds
80 in thermal paper products and their potential toxic effects (Goldinger et al. 2015;
81 Björnsdotter et al., 2017b; Eckardt and Simat, 2017) their migration and presence in the
82 environment have not been assessed so far.

83 Indoor dust is a potential source of human exposure to BPA and its analogs due
84 to their migration from many materials and slow degradation (Rudel et al., 2003; Völkel
85 et al., 2008; Geens et al., 2011 and 2012). Concentration values in indoor dust usually
86 range from $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ to $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ levels. Levels up to 39,000 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of BPA and up to 26,600
87 of BPS $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ have been reported in different countries from US and Asia (Liao et al.
88 2012b; Wang et al. 2015). In the present study, BPA replacements used in thermal
89 paper (BPF, BPS, BPS-MAE, D-8, TGSA) (Table 1) were analyzed in indoor dust for
90 the first time.

91 To carry out the study, a novel simultaneous extraction/clean-up method based
92 on the use of supramolecular solvents (SUPRASs) was optimized. SUPRASs are
93 nanostructured liquids produced from self-assembled amphiphilic compounds (Caballo
94 et al., 2017; Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018). They are excellent extraction materials
95 that offer multiple binding interactions (ionic, anionic, hydrogen bonds, dispersion
96 interactions, etc.). Binding interactions can be adjusted for each purpose by switching
97 the functional groups of the amphiphile and the nature of the coacervation-inducing
98 agent (Caballo et al., 2017; Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018). Their nanostructure give
99 rise to microenvironments of different polarity and confer them restricted access
100 properties for the exclusion of macromolecules, which are common interferents in
101 analytical applications (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2012). Further advantages are their
102 easy synthetic procedures, non-volatility and non-flammability (Caballo et al., 2017;
103 Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018). All these properties make them excellent candidates for
104 generic sample treatment of indoor dust, a complex and heterogeneous matrix
105 containing from textile and paper fibers to human or animal hair, cells and mineral
106 components, among others. Dust samples were collected in public environments,
107 because of the frequent use of thermal paper cash receipts. Results constitute a first
108 insight into the possible migration of these contaminants into the environment.

109

110 **2. Materials and methods**

111 *2.1. Chemicals and reagents*

112 All solvents were of analytical reagent-grade and were used as supplied.
113 Methanol (MeOH) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were acquired from VWR – Prolabo
114 Chemicals (Bois, France). 1- Octanol and 1- Decanol, were obtained from Sigma-
115 Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), while 1- Hexanol was supplied by Merck (Darmstadt,

116 Germany). Ultra-high-quality water was obtained from a Milli-Q water purification
117 system (Millipore, Madrid, Spain).

118 A standard reference material (SRM) Trace Metals - Baghouse Dust was used
119 for optimization and validation purposes. It was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St.
120 Louis, MO, USA).

121 The target compounds: 4,4'-(propane-2,2-diyl) diphenol (bisphenol A, BPA),
122 4,4'-Sulfonyldiphenol (bisphenol S, BPS) and 4,4'-Methylenediphenol (bisphenol F,
123 BPF) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). 4-(4-propan-2-
124 yloxyphenyl)sulfonylphenol (D-8), 4-(4-hydroxy-3-prop-2-enylphenyl)sulfonyl-2-prop-
125 2-enylphenol (TGSA) and 4-(4-phenylmethoxyphenyl)sulfonylphenol (BPS-MAE)
126 were obtained from Toronto Research Chemicals (Toronto, Canada). The internal
127 standards (IS) Bisphenol A-d₆ diglycidyl Ether (BPA-d₆) and bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-
128 Sulfone-d₈ (BPS-d₈) were also obtained from Toronto Research Chemicals.

129 Stock solutions of individual bisphenols (2 mg·mL⁻¹) were prepared in MeOH
130 and stored at -20°C. A spike solution of internal standards (BPS-d₈ and BPA-d₆) was
131 prepared in MeOH at a concentration of 5 mg·L⁻¹ for optimization and for sample
132 analysis. Intermediate and working solutions of bisphenols and of internal standards
133 mixtures were prepared by appropriate dilution in MeOH and stored at -20°C.

134

135 2.2. Apparatus

136 The analysis was carried out using an Agilent Technologies 1200 LC system
137 with a column Phenomenex Luna® C₈ column (2.0 mm i.d., 100 mm length, 3.0 μm
138 particle size) preceded by a precolumn Phenomenex KJ 0-4282 SecurityGuard Cartridge
139 Kit, Ea. This was coupled to an Agilent Technologies 6420 Triple Quadrupole mass

140 spectrometer equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in
141 negative mode. An additional LC column (Agilent Eclipse Plus C8 5 μm , 4.6 mm \times 50
142 mm) was inserted between the pump and injector in order to trap possible bisphenols
143 released from the instrument. Raw data was controlled and processed using Agilent
144 MassHunter Software® (version B.07.00).

145 Other instrumentation used for sample preparation were a vortex-shaker REAX
146 Top (Heidolph, Schwabach, Germany) and a 12 x 1.5 – 2 mL angle rotor Minicen
147 centrifuge from Ortoalresa (Madrid, Spain).

148

149 2.3. SUPRAS method optimization

150 Optimization of SUPRAS was carried out by extraction of a mix dust (collected
151 in two houses in Córdoba, sieved to 0.5 mm and homogenized), fortified at 5,000 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$
152 (BPA, BPF, BPS, D-8 and TGSA) and of internal standards (BPS- d_8 and BPA- d_6).

153 Dust aliquots (50 mg) were added to 2 mL Eppendorf microtubes, followed by
154 SUPRAS synthetic solutions (120 – 200 μL of amphiphile and a mixture of water:THF
155 up to 1.2 mL). Samples were vortex-stirred for 5 min for SUPRAS formation, sample
156 dispersion and extraction, and centrifuged for 20 min at 10,000 rpm for phase
157 separation. At the end, three phases were observed: SUPRAS (upper phase),
158 equilibrium solution (in the middle, containing water:THF and a residual amount of
159 amphiphile at the critical aggregation concentration) and the solid matrix (at the
160 bottom). The SUPRAS phase, enriched with the target compounds, was diluted to 1 mL
161 with MeOH to facilitate the optimization process by keeping constant the final volume
162 and aliquots of 3 μL were directly injected into the LC-MS/MS system.

163 Both the final composition and microstructure characteristics of the SUPRAS
164 depend on the nature and composition of the initial synthetic solution. A variety of
165 SUPRAS were generated with different amphiphiles and by tuning the composition of
166 the initial ternary mixture (amphiphile:water:THF) and tested for extraction. The
167 following experimental conditions were studied: type of amphiphile (1-hexanol, 1-
168 octanol and 1-decanol), concentration of amphiphile (10 – 16.67, % v/v) and
169 concentration of THF (8.33 – 33.33, % v/v) for a final volume of 1.2 mL. Experiments
170 were made in triplicate. Optimal conditions were selected on the basis of extraction
171 efficiency and concentration factor [SUPRAS volume (μL)/ sample size (mg)].

172

173 *2.4. SUPRAS method validation*

174 The linearity, detection and quantitation limits and matrix effects of the method
175 were assessed by running calibration with two dust samples, i.e. the in-house dust mix
176 and the SRM Trace Metals - Baghouse Dust, and at two sample sizes (25 and 50 mg).
177 Results were compared with those obtained from SUPRAS calibration. The optimal
178 SUPRAS (synthetic conditions: 200 μL 1-hexanol, 200 μL THF, 800 μL water) was
179 applied to dust samples fortified in the range 10 – 10,000 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of the target
180 compounds and 5,000 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of IS mix (mix of BPA-d₆ and BPS-d₈ at 5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$).
181 Unfortified SUPRAS (blanks) and dust samples were also analysed (in triplicate).
182 Levels of target compounds were below LODs in the blanks and in the two dust
183 samples.

184 The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) ($\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) of the method
185 were estimated from a signal-to-noise ratio of 3 and 10, respectively.

186

187 *2.5. Analysis of bisphenols*

188 2.5.1. *Sample collection*

189 Sampling was performed using a vacuum cleaner with bags. Samples were
190 collected in Spain in 2018 from public environments ($n=10$): two electronic shops, two
191 clothing shops, one sport clothing shop, one decoration shop, three bazaars and one
192 cafeteria. Samples were homogenized and sieved to 0.5 mm.

193

194 2.5.2. *Hexanol - based SUPRAS extraction*

195 First, approximately an aliquot of 25 mg of dust was weighed in a 2 mL
196 Eppendorf microtube. The SUPRAS synthetic solution (200 μ L of hexanol, 200 μ L of
197 THF and 800 μ L of water) was added and spiked with 25 μ L of IS mix. SUPRAS
198 formation and microextraction/clean-up was performed in a single-step by vortexing (5
199 min) and centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 20 min. After phase-separation, 150 μ L of
200 SUPRAS (the top layer) was collected, transferred to an LC vial and aliquots of 3 μ L
201 measured by LC MS/MS. A schema is shown in Figure 1.

202

203 2.5.3. *Quantification of bisphenols by LC – MS/MS*

204 The mobile phase was made up of Milli-Q water (A) and MeOH (B) at a flow
205 rate of 0.25 mL \cdot min⁻¹. The injection volume was 3 μ L. The gradient was as follow:
206 initial 100% A hold for 1 min and decreased to 30% in 5 min, holding for 7 min,
207 increased B to 100% and maintained for 6 min and finally re-conditioning for 7 min.

208 The MRM transitions for target masses are given in Table 2. BPA, BPF, BPS,
209 BPS-MAE, D-8 and TGSA were analyzed in ESI negative ionization mode.

210 The optimal source parameters were: gas temperature, 300 °C; gas flow, 11.0
211 L·min⁻¹; nebulizer gas pressure, 15 psi; capillary voltage, -4500 V; MS1 heater, 100 °C;
212 MS2 heater, 100 °C.

213 Quantitative analysis MassHunter workstation software from Agilent
214 Technologies was used for quantification of bisphenols. Calibration was performed with
215 SUPRAS in the range 10 – 10,000 ng·g⁻¹ and by using the deuterated internal standard
216 BPA-d₆, except for BPS, for which BPS-d₈ was used instead (at a final concentration of
217 5,000 ng·g⁻¹).

218

219 **3. Results and discussion**

220 SUPRASs have been already successfully applied in the extraction of bisphenols
221 from food (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2009), urine (García-Prieto et al. 2008; Salatti-
222 Dorado et al., 2016), environmental waters and wastewaters (Ballesteros Gómez et al.,
223 2007), etc.. SUPRASs are generated in a self-assembly and coacervation process that
224 occurs on two scales (Caballo et al., 2017; Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018). First,
225 amphiphiles form tridimensional aggregates (mainly micelles and/or vesicles) in
226 solution. Then, aggregates self-assemble into a new highly packed phase (SUPRAS) by
227 the stimuli of a coacervation-inducing agent (change of pH, temperature, addition of salt
228 or addition of a poor solvent for the amphiphile). They are very tunable solvents whose
229 composition and micro- or nano-structure change with the nature and composition of
230 the synthetic solution (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2012; Ballesteros-Gómez et al.,
231 2018). Both aspects influence recoveries of the target compounds and the simultaneous
232 exclusion of interferents (usually macromolecules or polymers which are non-soluble in
233 the SUPRAS medium or which are size-excluded due to the limited pore size of the
234 SUPRAS network). In general, amphiphiles with longer alkyl chain length give rise to

235 more hydrophobic SUPRAS, which have less content in water and which also provide
236 less energetic hydrogen bonds for extraction. Furthermore, SUPRAS with higher
237 content in water produce bigger coacervate droplets and less packed structures. This
238 usually results in better extraction efficiency for polar and moderate polar compounds,
239 such as bisphenols (Salatti-Dorado et al., 2016; Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2018). Phase
240 diagrams (for SUPRAS formation) and composition of SUPRAS made up of inverse
241 aggregates of 1-hexanol in THF:water have been recently reported by our group and
242 they have been proven to be suitable for the extraction of BPA (Salatti-Dorado et al.,
243 2016). For this reason they were selected for the study of novel BPA replacements.
244 SUPRAS formation just requires mixing and centrifuging the synthetic solution for
245 accelerating phase separation. Then, we observed two phases: the aqueous equilibrium
246 solution at the bottom (containing the residual alcohol at a low critical micellar
247 concentration) and the SUPRAS phase containing the majority of the amphiphile
248 packed as an inverse hexagonal phase. Figure 2 shows a schema of the SUPRAS
249 formation and its structure. The equilibrium solution helped to disperse the sample and
250 favored the extraction process at such a low volume of SUPRAS phase (usually 100 –
251 500 μ L). Furthermore, it acts as sink of polar interferents.

252

253 *3.1. SUPRAS optimization*

254 As preliminary experiments, SUPRAS blanks (without dust) were underwent
255 extraction by changing the type of amphiphile (1-hexanol, 1-octanol and 1-decanol, in a
256 range of 10 – 16.67, % v/v) under different percentages of THF (8.33, 16.67, 25 and
257 33.33, % v/v) in order to establish the recovery of the target compounds against the
258 equilibrium solution. Figure 3 shows the recoveries of analytes (BPA, BPF, BPS, BPS-
259 MAE, D-8 and TGSA) for each amphiphile using 120 μ L of amphiphile (10% v/v).

260 Considering the alkyl chain length, recoveries decreased with an increasing number of
261 carbon atoms. Although 1-octanol had similar recoveries than 1-hexanol for some
262 analytes, the latter provided good extraction efficiency in a wider polarity range. The
263 higher recoveries with SUPRAS of shorter alkyl-chain length amphiphiles can be
264 attributed to both strongest hydrogen bonds for extraction, as explained above, and
265 smaller aggregate sizes offering a higher contact surface for binding the contaminants.
266 As shown in Figure 3, the percentage of THF did not influence recoveries so
267 significantly in the tested range. SUPRAS volumes increased exponentially with the
268 THF percentage (see Table S1), so that the concentration factor also dropped. For this
269 reason, an intermediate value of 16.67% v/v THF was set as optimal for further
270 experiments.

271 Once the optimal amphiphile and THF percentages were selected, we evaluated
272 different volumes of 1-hexanol to form the SUPRAS. Recoveries were expected to
273 increase with the percentage of amphiphile and concentration factors to decrease
274 linearly (as SUPRAS volumes increased). Experiments were carried out in the presence
275 of dust (50 mg) with SUPRASs formed with 120, 150 and 200 μL of amphiphile (10,
276 12.5 and 16.67% v/v, respectively). Recoveries were maximal with 200 μL of 1-hexanol
277 and were of 93 ± 3 for BPA, 77 ± 4 for BPS, 88 ± 2 for BPF, 80 ± 2 for D-8 and 82 ± 3
278 for TGSA. These values were just slightly lower than without dust at the same 1-
279 hexanol percentage (see figure S1). Under these conditions the SUPRAS volume extract
280 was of 207 μL (calculated as specified in Table S1).

281

282 3.2. Analytical performance and validation

283 Calibration curves were prepared in SUPRAS ($10 - 10,000 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, $n=11$, $5,000 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of
284 IS mix). As can be seen in Table 3, the correlation coefficients were in the range 0.9597

285 – 0.9993. Method detection (MDL) and quantification (MQL) limits were estimated
286 considering a signal to noise ratio of 3 and 10, respectively, and were in the range 0.5 –
287 10 and 1 – 20 ng·g⁻¹, respectively.

288 Calibration curves were also run in the presence of two dust samples (mix dust
289 and SRM Baghouse dust) at two sample sizes (25 and 50 mg) to validate the
290 methodology at the same spiking levels (10 – 10,000 ng·g⁻¹, *n*=11). Matrix effects were
291 calculated as the ratio from both slopes (SUPRAS_{with dust}/SUPRAS x 100) and were
292 acceptable and in the ranges 70 – 100% and 86-120% for the dust mix and the SRM,
293 respectively, at 25 mg, so that this sample size was considered as optimal. Correlation
294 coefficients were in the range 0.9651 – 0.9961 and 0.9915 – 0.9995 for the dust mix and
295 the SRM, respectively. SUPRAS blanks and unfortified dust samples did not contain
296 detectable levels of the target compounds.

297

298 *3.3. Extraction of bisphenols in real samples.*

299 Ten indoor dust samples collected from different public environments and they
300 were analyzed by the validated SUPRAS method. Table 4 shows the concentration
301 range, mean, median and detection percentages for each analyte. In Table S2 the
302 concentrations of the target compounds and the IS recoveries in each sample is
303 specified. IS recoveries varied in the ranges 71 – 108 and 69 – 95% for BPA-d₆ and
304 BPS-d₈, respectively. BPA was the most abundant bisphenol detected in all the samples,
305 with a mean of 1,883 ng·g⁻¹ followed by BPS (203 ng·g⁻¹) and BPF (70 ng·g⁻¹), which
306 are their most used analogs in the industry. These concentrations are well in agreement
307 with those reported in other countries (see Table S3). For example, concentrations for
308 BPA in the literature ranges from 630 to 3,260 ng·g⁻¹ (median) (Liao et al., 2012) and
309 from 100 to 3,800 ng·g⁻¹ (mean) (Wang et al., 2015); for BPF ranges from 38 to 450

310 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (median) (Liao et al., 2012) and from 1.9 to 5,500 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (mean) (Wang et al.,
311 2015) and for BPS ranges from 170 to 810 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (median) (Liao et al., 2012) and from
312 <2 to 1,500 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (mean) (Wang et al., 2015). In this study levels were in the ranges
313 192 – 4,444 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, 29 – 183 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and <0.075 – 736 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for BPA, BPS and BPF,
314 respectively.

315 Emerging BPA replacements (BPS-MAE, D-8 and TGSA), which are for the
316 first time reported in this study, were detected in 50%, 70% and 90% of the dust
317 samples, respectively. They were less abundant than BPS and BPF, with medians
318 between 6 and 22 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (around ten-fold lower values). This suggests that they are
319 used in lower amounts or in fewer types of materials or that their migration is slower
320 than that of the other bisphenols. We could not find information about other uses than
321 thermal paper.

322

323 **4. Conclusions**

324 The emerging BPA replacements (BPS-MAE, D-8 and TGSA) were detected for
325 the first time in indoor dust, at median levels around ten times lower than BPS but
326 frequently detected (50 – 90%). These replacements have previously been reported as
327 colour developers in thermal paper. The SUPRAS method is suitable as generic sample
328 treatment of indoor dust, the procedure was simple and fast (5 min stirring + 20 min
329 centrifugation), recoveries were within the required levels (69 – 108%) and LODs were
330 satisfactory for this matrix (in the low $\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). Results show the potential of these
331 emerging contaminants to migrate into the environment and constitute a first insight
332 into their presence in indoor dust as a relevant route of exposure. It is worthy to monitor
333 these compounds in future studies taken into account the limited number of samples and
334 the fact that they seems to be frequently present, specially taken into account that they

335 are considered toxic (TGSA, D-8) and very toxic (BPS-MAE) to aquatic life according
336 to the data available on the ECHA database.

337

338 **Acknowledgements**

339 Authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from Spanish Ministry of Science,
340 Innovation and Universities (Project CTQ2017-83823R). A. Ballesteros-Gómez
341 acknowledges the funding from Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and
342 Universities for a Ramón y Cajal contract (RYC-2015-18482).

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492 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

493 **Figure 1.** Schema of SUPRAS method for the determination of emerging BPA
494 replacements in indoor dust samples.

495 **Figure 2.** Schema of the synthesis of the SUPRAS made up of 1-hexanol in THF:water
496 mixtures, which involves processes of self-assembly and coacervation.

497 **Figure 3.** Extraction efficiency of target compounds with SUPRAS based on
498 amphiphiles of different alkyl chain length (C6, C8 and C10) under different
499 percentages of THF and expressed as mean \pm SD ($n=3$). Conditions: blanks (dust: 0
500 mg), concentration of amphiphile (10% v/v), concentration of THF (8.33 – 33.33, %
501 v/v), final volume of 1.2 mL.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Table 1. Compound name and CAS number, molecular structure, chemical formula, monoisotopic mass and log P of BPA, BPS, BPF, BPS-MAE, D-8 and TGSA

Compound & CAS	Molecular structure	Chemical formula	Monoisotopic mass (g/mol)	Log P
4,4'-(propane-2,2-diyl)diphenol (BPA) 80-05-7		C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂	228.115	3.32 ^a 3.3 ^b
4,4'-Sulfonyldiphenol (BPS) 80-09-1		C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄	250.030	1.9 ^b
4,4'-Methylenediphenol (BPF) 620-92-8		C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₂	200.084	2.91 ^a 2.9 ^b
4-(4-propan-2-yloxyphenyl)sulfonylphenol (D-8) 95235-30-6		C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄ S	292.077	3 ^b
4-(4-hydroxy-3-prop-2-enylphenyl)sulfonyl-2-prop-2-enylphenol (TGSA) 41481-66-7		C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ S	330.093	4.1 ^b
4-((4-(Allyloxy)phenyl)sulfonyl)phenol (BPS-MAE) 97042-18-7		C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ S	290.0607	2.9 ^b

LogP values obtained from PubChem, ^aexperimental, ^bcalculated

Table 2. MRM transitions, dwell time, fragmentor voltage and collision energy. Quantifiers for target compounds are indicated in bold

Compound	Precursor ion (m/z)	Product ion (m/z)	Dwell time (ms)	Fragmentor (V)	Collision energy (eV)	Polarity
BPA	227.1	212.2	50	100	20	Negative
BPA	227.1	113.0	50	100	24	Negative
BPF	199.0	105.0	50	100	25	Negative
BPF	199.0	93.0	50	100	30	Negative
BPS	249.0	108.0	50	100	20	Negative
BPS	249.0	92.1	50	100	32	Negative
BPS-MAE	289.1	248.1	50	100	20	Negative
BPS-MAE	289.1	184.1	50	100	30	Negative
D8	291.1	248.0	50	100	25	Negative
D8	291.1	184.1	50	100	25	Negative
TGSA	329.1	132.1	50	100	25	Negative
TGSA	329.1	148.1	50	100	25	Negative

Table 3. Analytical performance of the SUPRAS-based calibration^a

	Slope (ua g·ng⁻¹) ± Error	Lineal range (ng·g⁻¹)	R²	LOD (ng·g⁻¹)	LOQ (ng·g⁻¹)
BPA	0.000151 ± 3·10 ⁻⁶	20-10,000	0.9977	10	20
BPS	0.0020 ± 0.0001	2-10,000	0.9872	1	2
BPF	0.000081 ± 2·10 ⁻⁶	20-10,000	0.9962	10	20
D8	0.012 ± 0.001	2-10,000	0.9597	1	2
TGSA	0.0015 ± 0.0001	2-10,000	0.9759	1	2
BPS-MAE	0.00309 ± 3·10 ⁻⁵	1-10,000	0.9993	0.5	1

^aIS mix at 5,000 ng/g, *n*=11, weight 1/*x*, origin included

Table 4. Concentration of target compounds (in ng·g⁻¹) found in indoor dust samples from different public microenvironment in Spain (n=10)

	BPA	BPF	BPS	BPS- MAE	D8	TGSA
Concentration range	192 - 4444	Detected - 183	n.d. - 736	n.d. - 79	n.d. - 58	n.d. - 48
Mean^a	1883	79	290	20	23	22
Median^b	1739	60	193	6	20	22
Detection percentage (%)	100	100	70	50	70	90

n.d.: non-detected

^a: Calculated without values below the LOQ

^b: Calculated without values below the LOQ